

Effect of Corrosive Media on Hardness and Wear resistance of $\text{Li}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5$ glass-ceramics

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ABSTRACT

The influence of corrosion in an acidic (4% acetic acid (pH=2.4)) and a basic media of NaOH (pH=10) on microhardness of lithium disilicate dental ceramics was studied. Three types of lithium disilicate glass ceramics were prepared by sintering of partially crystallized lithium metasilicate glass ceramics, with subsequent crystallization of lithium disilicate using two different two-stage heat treatment regimes: A - 500°C/2 h, + 850°C/2 h; B - 500°C/1 h + 820°C/1 h; and a one stage heat treatment C – 850 °C/1h. In all cases the heating and cooling rates were 5°C/min and 5°C/min, respectively. The temperatures were determined on the basis of data obtained from literature, where the first temperature was applied to nucleate lithium disilicate, while the second temperature was used to grow the lithium disilicate crystals. This way the materials with various mechanical properties and corrosion resistance were prepared.

The influence of corrosion in acidic and basic media on properties of dental glass ceramics was monitored on the basis of results of the tests carried out both under quasi-dynamic and static conditions. The quasi-dynamic test was performed at the temperature corresponding to the temperature of human body (37°C). In both media, the samples were corroded for 96 h with exchange of the corrosion medium for a fresh one in 12 h intervals. Under static conditions the samples were tested at 80°C for 16 h without a change of the corrosion medium of 4% acetic acid (ISO 6872, Standards for hydrolytic resistance of dental ceramics materials).

The microhardness was determined by Vickers indentation at the load of 1.0 N on mechanically polished surfaces of dental ceramics before and after corrosion. The microhardness of materials A and B was identical (for A: 625±4 HV1.0, for B: 625±8 HV1.0). For the material C slightly lower value was measured (607±10 HV1.0). After static corrosion test in 4% acetic acid the Vickers hardness of material A decreased from 625±4 HV1.0 to 594±4 HV1.0. After dynamic test in the same corrosion medium the decrease was less pronounced, to 605±8 HV1.0. Dynamic corrosion test in basic solution with pH 10 led to decrease of microhardness to 599±13 HV1.0. The corrosion in basic or acidic solutions had no significant impact on microhardness of materials B and C. The contents of the elements leached into the solution of corrosion media during corrosion were determined by atomic emission spectrometry (AES) with inductively coupled plasma. The major elements leached from dental ceramics were lithium, phosphorus and potassium in the acidic environment, and phosphorus, lithium and silicon in basic solutions. Highest resistance against corrosion acid environment was measured for the material B. Corrosion resistance in alkaline medium was similar for all materials. Wear resistance of both corroded and un-corroded materials was tested by tribometry measurements in dry conditions using ball-on-flat technique. The tribological partner was a highly polished alumina ball 6.35 mm in diameter, the applied load was 10 N, sliding speed 10 cm/s and sliding distance was 50 m. Wear of uncorroded materials A and B was the same ($5.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$), wear of the un-corroded material C was slightly lower ($5.5 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$). The corrosion both in basic or acidic environment under dynamic conditions caused a decrease in wear resistance of all tested samples. Wear of material A was after corrosion in basic environment $6.0 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$, in acidic environment $6.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4 \times 10^{-5}$. Wear

of material B increased after corrosion in basic solution to $5.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8 \times 10^{-5}$, after corrosion in 4% acetic acid to $6.4 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6 \times 10^{-5}$. Wear of C increased from $5.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ to $6.5 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ after corrosion in acidic medium and to $6.3 \times 10^{-4} \pm 10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ in NaOH solution. However, the corrosion test according to the ISO 6872 led to an increase in wear resistance. Wear decreased from $5.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4 \times 10^{-5}$ to $5.4 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ for material A, from $5.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4 \times 10^{-5}$ to $5.4 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ for B and from $5.5 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5 \times 10^{-5}$ to $4.5 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ for C material. The decrease could cause the formation of a lubrication layer of the non-analyzed composition. After extended contact with acidic or basic solutions all studied ceramic materials displayed evidence of surface structural changes, as confirmed by examination of corroded surfaces by scanning electron microscopy. Degradation of micromechanical properties, i.e. decrease of wear resistance (dynamic corrosion conditions) and of Vickers microhardness (material A) was confirmed.

Keywords: lithium disilicate dental ceramics, corrosion, microhardness, wear resistance

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